

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

gEneSys. Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems

WP6 – Dissemination and Impact

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND IMPACT STRATEGY

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Table of Content

Revised and updated overview of the gEneSys dissemination and impact strategy 4

Explaining how gEneSys is meeting the challenges highlighted in the Horizon Europe Call under which the projects was funded. 9

gEneSys objectives and organisation 9

Objectives of the dissemination and impact (D&I) work package, WP6 10

Management and organisation of the D&I strategy 11

Sharing experiences, results, and goals with target communities 11

Expected impacts of gEneSys 12

Promoting understanding of energy transition as a socio-technical innovation ecosystem 12

Policy subsystem 12

Economic subsystem 13

Environmental subsystem 13

Socio-cultural subsystem 13

Governance subsystem 13

Technological subsystem 14

Learning from the efforts of past projects 14

Building relations with current projects and programmes 14

Tracking gEneSys impact 15

Target beneficiaries of gEneSys results and knowledge they may need 15

Adding value in exploitation of results 18

Dialogue and knowledge sharing with stakeholders in energy 19

Promoting the Gendered Innovations analytical framework 19

Dialogue focused on the policy subsystem 20

Participating in the dialogue focused on the technology subsystem 21

Participating in the dialogue focused on society 21

Participating in the dialogue focused on environment 21

Participating in the dialogue focused on governance 22

Participation in the dialogue focused on Africa and SDGs 22

On-line access to key resources 22

Conferences and events 23

Communication 23

Website 24

Communication channels and materials 25

Revised and updated overview of the gEneSys dissemination and impact strategy

The aim of D.6.2 is to refine the gEneSys strategy on where and how to place the project and its work to create the desired impact. This document is a revised and updated version of the text introduced in D.6.1, which was in the 8th month of the project. The emphasis here is on using gEneSys research, its other work, and the lessons learned since the start. At the mid-point of the project we are well aware that the EU energy transition landscape is crowded with multitude of public and private organisations, programmes, policies, projects and events pursuing specific agendas, that are overwhelmingly technologically-focused and 'blind' to gender knowledge, and all competing intensely for the attention of policy and decision makers.

The gEneSys strategy for dissemination and impact is purposefully distinct because it advocates for the integration of gender knowledge into the design and implementation of interventions for energy transition. Being 'blind' to gender knowledge, which is the case in the majority of past and current interventions, means missing opportunities to produce achievable gender equality benefits. All societies are gendered in some way, which means that women and men may regularly experience different opportunities and outcomes shaping their lives. Therefore, when energy transition interventions claim justice, fairness, equity, and sustainability as their core motivations, they should routinely examine gender inequalities in their goals and opportunities to make impact. The 2024 [JRC study](#) on "*Gender and Energy: The effects of the energy transition on women*" recommends that strong data collection and monitoring methods for tracking the success of gender-inclusive energy transition activities are needed to enable informed and targeted interventions, at both the national and European levels.

The European Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW) exemplifies the 'blind' to gender knowledge attitude. In the last two years, there was only one session on gender issues. And, although, the 2024 EUSEW introduced the Award for Women in Energy, which "*recognises women who lead outstanding activities that, if replicated, help to advance the clean energy transition in Europe... resulting in wider social, economic and environmental benefits*" this action, whilst admirable in itself, will not achieve the [systemic mainstreaming of gender equality across all EU programmes](#). The 2020 report on [gender impact assessments of the EU Recovery Plan](#), commissioned by members of the European Parliament, identified wide range of failures to mainstream gender equality into the European Recovery and Resilience Facility, Invest EU, the Strategic Investment Facility, and the EU4Health programme.

During 2021-2027 MFF negotiations, equality between man and women was agreed as a Horizontal Principle of the Budget and the Commission committed in December 2020 to develop a methodology to measure gender relevant expenditure at programme level in the MFF 2021-2027. [The analysis by the Commission](#) of the 49 MFF-funded programmes shows that 13 programmes included interventions with gender equality as principal objective; 6 programmes have interventions with gender equality as a significant objectives; 21 programmes have a likely but as yet unclear impact on gender equality; and 9 programmes have no significant impact on gender equality. The programmes are assessed on the scale of '2', '1', '0*' and '0'. where '2' is allocated to cases with gender equality as the principal objective, and '0' is allocated to programmes with no significant impact on gender equality. This is shown in the figure below.

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

The fact that 21 major EU programmes have "a likely but yet unclear impact on gender equality" means that these programmes could be advanced to the higher level of '1' with the help of gender knowledge and expert advice to become "[where gender equality is a significant objective](#)".

Therefore, the energy transition related MFF-funded programmes represent an important dissemination target for gEneSys.

Since gEneSys envisages energy transition as a socio-technological research and innovation ecosystem, made up of several interconnected sub-systems each with its own priorities and power structures and relations (see p12), this means that in the group of the [21 programmes rated at the 0* level](#) there potentially are several differently oriented programmes that have a direct or indirect connection to the gEneSys' goal of transforming gendered interrelations of power and inequality in the pathways to energy transition.

The MFF-funded programmes of particular interest to gEneSys include: Horizon Europe (the parts with the biggest budget), Invest EU, Digital Europe, EU4Health, European Social Fund, Erasmus, Just Transition, and Citizenship Equality Rights and Values. Involved in these programmes are several different DGs: DG ECFIN, DG CNECT, DG RTD, DG SANTE, DG EMPL, DG CINEA, DG ENER, DG EAC, DG JUSTICE. Some of these DGs have themselves sponsored research on gender issues to inform their own policy domain. This research will complement and expand the research conducted in gEneSys. For example, DG ECFIN, which is responsible for the Invest EU programme, has published in July 2020 a study on [Gender Smart Financing. Investing In and With Women: Opportunities for Europe](#), to which DG RTD, DG GROW and DG EMPL have also made a contribution.

Outlined in the table below, are suggestions on how gEneSys research can be connected to the EU policy on mainstreaming gender equality in policy areas relevant to energy transition.

Dissemination and impact objectives as defined in the project proposal	Connecting gEneSys research to the EU policy on mainstreaming gender equality
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D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

<p>To support the overall objectives and activities of the project following best practice communication and its dissemination strategies and ensure that all project results are made available to all potential change actors, stakeholders, and change recipients, as well as promoting project partners' expertise and experience.</p>	<p><i>The research reported in D.1.2 applied a gender perspective to examine scientific influence of the communities involved in the production of knowledge on energy transition knowledge. The aim was to identify in which research areas the influence was higher for women, in which for men, and in which there was gender balance. The findings indicate that overall the field is strongly dominated by men and in particular in the governance and technology sub-fields. Women make a significant contribution to the knowledge on environment and behaviour subfields.</i></p> <p>These findings are relevant to developing human and intellectual capital for energy transition efforts and ensuring societal support for the 'greening' of economies, and therefore DG EAC, DG RTD, DG EMPL. They are also relevant to the decisions on priority calls in future phases of Horizon Europe, and to the monitoring of progress on gender equality in energy-related programmes.</p>
<p>To broaden the engagement with the multiple target audiences in participatory discourse and processes to achieve consensus on credible pathways and solutions to energy transition with equitable, fair, and just outcomes, focused on intersectional perspective on gender inequality.</p>	<p><i>The analysis of the results from the systematic literature review on energy-gender nexus shows seven dimensions in which the link between gender and energy occur, namely empowerment, employment/work, attitudes/behaviour, transition to modern energy, knowledge/awareness, perception, and health. These results reveal that the energy transition could potentially reduce the gender inequalities embedded in the traditional energy sector if a just transition is achieved.</i></p> <p><i>Additional knowledge is being gained through joint discussions between gEneSys and related projects, e.g., LEAP-RE, to help strengthen their contribution to gender equality.</i></p> <p>These results are relevant to the planning of future Calls in Horizon Europe; advancement of interdisciplinary research training. e.g. through MSCAs, incorporating gender equality actions in the programmes designed to promote research for societal progress; EU policy on widening and SDGs implementation.</p>
<p>To coordinate project tie-ins to other projects and to the evolving EU energy and equality policy agendas, and to highlight the importance of European collaboration.</p>	<p><i>The research reported in D.1.2 presents a comparative analysis of National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRPs) across EU member states, examining their incorporation of 'green deal' provisions, gender equality, and energy transition goals. The aim was to assess how effectively gender equality, diversity, and inclusion are addressed and how well EU countries uphold equality principles established in national, European, and international gender equality strategies.</i></p>

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

	<p>These results are relevant to the Commission's policy to establish gender equality as a cross-cutting objective for all policy areas, as well as the implementation of Next Generation EU recovery plan more gender sensitive, and promote gender mainstreaming and gender budgeting as beneficial tools in the multiannual financial framework 2021-2027. The results are also relevant to the planning of experts consultations expected to recommend institutional actions to accelerate energy transitions processes, which in the past tended to be 'gender blind'.</p>
<p>To work with change actors and stakeholders in Africa and in international context to advance gender equality goal of the UN Sustainable Development Agenda 2030 and in research for energy transition</p>	<p><i>The research reported in D.4.1. provides detailed analysis of EU-Africa cooperation in energy and climate change initiatives, with a strong focus on gender integration. It reveals a complex landscape of opportunities and challenges. These initiatives demonstrate a significant commitment to sustainable development, climate action, and gender equality, aligning with global goals and regional ambitions. However, the incorporation of gender considerations varies across initiatives, highlighting the need for more systematic and explicit integration of gender perspectives to ensure equitable benefits and participation.</i></p> <p>These results are relevant to the Commission efforts to research agreements between the EU and countries in Africa, e.g., as part of Horizon Europe, science diplomacy, as for External Services in cooperation on development driven by scientific knowledge</p>
<p>Engage and consult the Advisory Board in consensus building decision making, who have been selected for their specific areas of expertise that matched the aims of the Work Plan,</p>	<p><i>The conclusions from the research conducted so far are that even when gender is a topic of research few studies use the collected evidence and data to make recommendations for policy on achieving gender equality benefits from energy transition efforts.</i></p> <p>The question how to advance programmes rated '0*' to '1' will be explored with the Advisory Board members and through collaborative knowledge sharing activities with key player organisations and projects operating in the energy transition ecosystem.</p>

Review of the gEneSys communication messages intended to help explain what gEneSys is about, and why it is needed

<p>What needs does gEneSys responds to</p>	<p>The project responds to the gender equality imperatives in the EU programmes that directly or indirectly relate to energy transition efforts in the EU, such as Horizon Europe, InvestEU,</p>
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D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

	<p>Digital Europe, EU4Health, European Social Fund, Erasmus, Just Transition, Citizenship Equality Rights and Values</p> <p>The project is also responding to the opportunities to advance gender equality benefits in the energy transition efforts in Africa, specially where mechanisms for EU-Africa cooperation in science and technology, or development policy, already exist.</p>
<p>What problem will gEneSys help solve</p>	<p>The project recognises that current approaches to energy transition rely overwhelmingly on technological solutions and are 'blind' to gender knowledge. This means that opportunities to produce gender equality benefits are being missed. Furthermore, the mainstreaming of gender equality benefits in the EU programmes has not matched the EU policy commitments to advancing gender equality as a horizontal issue for the whole EU budget.</p> <p>In general, the connection between gender equality and energy policy is under-researched. gEneSys will identify gaps in knowledge at the nexus between policies on gender equality and energy transition and make recommendations where new research is needed and what the existing research says about achieving gender equality benefits.</p>
<p>What new understanding and evidence will gEneSys generate</p>	<p>The project will provide measurable, verifiable, and achievable outcomes by building evidence, scholarly understanding, identifying power holders and facilitating international cooperation between Europe and Africa. The project will advance interdisciplinary, mixed quantitative and qualitative analytical approaches combined with participatory elements and application of gendered innovation analysis.</p>
<p>Who will benefit from gEneSys activities and outputs</p>	<p>The primary target are policy makers across all the sectors of energy transition efforts, involved in particular in shaping and managing the programmes funded under the EU Multiannual Financial Framework, as well as projects and others specific interventions that these programmes fund. Additional target are women as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, citizens, and consumers directly involved in knowledge production or its uses. Benefiting also are those involved in education who are responsible for ensuring quality and impact through pedagogic methods, curricula, and textbooks.</p>
<p>What outcomes will be achieved</p>	<p>gEneSys will demonstrate gender equality as a lever rather than a barrier to achieving fair, just and equitable energy transition outcomes, and will promote actions on gender equality as a goal of the energy transition processes, connecting energy transition</p>

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

	with the goals of the EU Green Deal, climate change mitigation and SDGs implementation.
How will the objectives and results be shared outside gEneSys	gEneSys will engage multiple target audiences, made up of actors, stakeholders, and participants in energy transition, who share and jointly shape the vision and progress on achieving low-carbon future. The project will help integrate considerations of gender in the science-society-policy dialogue on energy issues and raise awareness of interrelationships of power and intersectional aspects of gender inequality. It will organise two international conference events and create tie-ins with relevant other projects and policy agendas, as well as host a Summer School at Venice International University.

Explaining how gEneSys is meeting the challenges highlighted in the Horizon Europe Call under which the projects was funded.

The relevant Horizon Europe Call text specified that proposals are expected to develop a theoretical framework to understand the formation of gendered power hierarchies leading to systematic and structural forms of discriminations, social and economic inequalities, and gender-based violence and should relate this to developing solutions on how to address inequalities and underlying causes related to society's perception and construction of gender norms, masculinities, femininities, and gender diverse identities. The specific expectations in the Call text include:

- Analysis of the interrelations of power and barriers to gender equality between different social and economic issues including, inter alia: policy and decision-making, labour market participation and the gender pay gap, workplace, and work-life balance arrangements.
- Considerations of how intersectionality of gender with, e.g., ethnicity, social origin, religion, disability, and sexual orientation impacts one's position and rights in society and social hierarchy, as well as one's life and career choices.
- Developing solutions into how to address inequalities and underlying causes related to society's perception and construction of gender norms and representations.
- Promoting international cooperation, as well as the development of social innovation approaches, which can foster new social practices, social ownership, or market uptake.
- Promoting actions to dismantle structural and systematic roots of unequal power distribution between women and men on all levels and promote women's social and economic empowerment. Particular attention should be paid to differing cultural contexts across the EU and among Associated and third countries.

The project conceptualises energy transition as a gendered socio-technical innovation ecosystem emerging out of the interplay between the technological, policy, social, environmental, governance and economic subsystems. The power relations and inequalities that gEneSys will address will be those within each subsystem, at the intersections between different subsystem, and the system as an ecosystem.

gEneSys objectives and organisation

gEneSys advances understanding of gender and social inequalities in energy transition policies, processes, and outcomes through new research and by closing knowledge gaps in how gender fits into the vision and realisations of just and fair energy transition resulting in the clean, affordable, and secure energy sources and services. This goal relates also to the UN Sustainable Development Agenda 2030, and especially SDG7, which targets “access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy”. In this context gEneSys will cooperate with partners in Africa. In all these cases, the relevant texts are ‘gender blind’ in that they don’t ask for gender-related indicators and don’t specify gender targets. In addition to raising awareness of and supplying new evidence on gender inequality issues in energy transition, gEneSys will improve understanding of “intersectionality” as a research analytical tool as well as a social justice goal.

gEneSys conceptualises energy transition as a dynamic, gendered, mission-oriented socio-technical innovation ecosystem with technological, social, environmental, governance, and economic subsystems, each with its own sustainability visions, implementation concerns, power relations, values and priorities, as well as change actors and stakeholders.

More specifically, gEneSys will respond to the challenges identified in the Horizon Europe Call by:

- cooperating with partners in Africa through its own African partner, the African Institute for Mathematical Science, and external collaborating organisations and/or projects working towards the EU’s and UN’s mission to supply/ensure access to affordable and secure energy, and to show how to integrate gender perspectives into implementations of SDG7 targets and achieve gender equality benefits.
- improving understanding of “inclusion” by raising awareness of the intersectional aspects of gender inequality in relation to energy transition through the analysis of existing data and by collecting, analysing, and theorising original data collected through extensive surveys.
- reviewing EU and national energy-related frameworks to identify the extent to which gender mainstreaming is being implemented.
- examining available statistics on the participation and roles that women hold in energy-related sectors as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and employees. It will also collect new data to understand the behaviours and attitudes to energy transition of women and men as citizens and consumers.
- assembling gender evidence base for transformative climate and environmental policies with an intersectional approach to reduce climate and environmental impacts while challenging patriarchal and other discriminatory structures.
- applying gender lens to the 400 priority SSH research questions recommended by the EU Energy SHIFTS project to support appropriately designed studies with intersectional aspects of gender dimension fully considered.
- improving understanding how countries can use the shift towards sustainable energy to tackle systemic gender discrimination within societies.

Objectives of the dissemination and impact (D&I) work package, WP6

The overarching aim of WP6 is to promote (through multiple communication channels), support (e.g., designing and organising participatory events), and enhance opportunities for exploitation of

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

the work and results of gEneSys to demonstrate how gender equality and gender dimensions in research can improve design and implementation of energy transition pathways and processes to achieve sustainability and outcomes that are equitable, just, and fair.

The specific objectives of the dissemination activities are:

- To share information about project objectives, activities and results and make them available to all potential change actors, stakeholders, and change recipients, as well creating opportunities to enhance project partners' expertise, experience, and status in the research community.
- To ensure engagement with multiple target audiences through participatory dialogue and activities aimed at achieving consensus on credible pathways and solutions to energy transition with equitable, fair, and just outcomes, and advancing intersectional perspective on energy related gender and social inequalities.
- To coordinate project tie-ins to other projects and to the evolving EU energy and equality policy agendas, and to highlight the importance of European collaboration in achieving gender equality.
- To work with change actors and stakeholders in Africa and in international context to advance gender equality goal of the UN Sustainable Development Agenda 2030 and in research for energy transition.
- To engage and consult the Advisory Board, who have been selected for their specific areas of expertise that matched the aims of the Work Plan, in consensus building decision making.

Management and organisation of the D&I strategy

Portia is tasked with the overall leadership and management of the work towards the objectives of WP6, with all other partners acting as co-leads and or contributors. In total, WP6 include five distinct Tasks. One task is dedicated to supporting the project partners; three tasks are dedicated to engaging with multiple target audiences in the energy transition ecosystem; and one task is dedicated to hosting a Summer School, which is led by VIU and CNR.

Sharing experiences, results, and goals with target communities

During the first 18 months, gEneSys established direct connections and collaborations with several projects, initiatives and programmes in the energy transition socio-technical innovation ecosystem, which have either 1) already developed support measures for gender equality, or 2) plan/wish to do so, or 3) have not considered gender equality as relevant to their mission but should do so (e.g., if receiving funding as part of the EU Cohesion strategy or Horizon Europe).

The purpose of these relationships is for gEneSys to introduce new research and to offer recommendations on how to advance and harmonise understanding and activities related to the questions below:

- How to overcome gender inequalities in existing energy systems, and how to prevent these inequalities occurring in the renewable and low carbon energy systems?
- How to mainstream gender into new policy frameworks that underpin energy transition and European Green Deal?

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

- How to integrate gender perspective into energy transition processes and outcomes, including the targets of the UN Sustainable Development Goals Agenda 2030?
- How to advance women in energy ecosystem as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, leaders, employees, and consumers?
- How to measure and monitor gender equality in relation to achieving justice and fairness in energy transition outcomes?
- How to promote shared values of equity, sustainability, participation, and diversity across the social, economic, environmental, and technical spheres of energy transition?
- How to respond to intersectional dimensions of gender equality in societal debates on access to energy, energy security, energy poverty and affordability, environmental impacts, etc.?
- How social innovation can facilitate transformations of existing power hierarchies in energy transition planning and management?
- How can research help facilitate greater societal acceptance of the changes on people's lives created by energy transition measures, and how to fully include women at all levels of energy-related knowledge production, application, and communication?
- How can approaches and understanding of energy transition processes be made more sensitive to gender issues through systematic gender mainstreaming, gender budgeting, use of Gendered Innovations analysis, Multistakeholder Partnerships, Communities of Practice, Gender Equality Plans, Responsible Research & Innovation?

Expected impacts of gEneSys

Promoting understanding of energy transition as a socio-technical innovation ecosystem

gEneSys conceptualises energy transition as a dynamic, gendered, mission-oriented socio-technical innovation ecosystem with several 'subsystems': technological, policy, social, environmental, governance, and economic, each with its own sustainability visions, values, and priorities, as well as change actors and stakeholder, who may also influence what happens in other subsystems.

Policy subsystem

Many disparities and inequalities between the sexes have become historically embedded in the baseline of public policies and in the allocation of public resources. The EU is officially committed to mainstreaming gender equality into policymaking together with targeted actions to tackle gender-blindness and gender-bias in policy design and practice. Gender mainstreaming and environmental policy integration are both EU treaty-based obligations. This means that gender equality and environmental objectives must be mainstreamed or integrated into all areas of EU policymaking, including sectors where they are not immediately obvious. Of particular interest are the concerns that the most recent policy frameworks, e.g., the EU Just Transition Mechanism, LIFE Clean Energy Transition, and REPower still appear to be gender blind.

Economic subsystem

Compared to other parts of the economy, energy is one of the most gender unequal sectors. Women are underrepresented in both traditional and emerging energy sectors, at all levels. Much of the discourse on the effects of energy transition has focused on the impact on men's jobs and on their skills needs for future jobs. Jobs in renewable energy tend to be scattered across different areas of employment, such as manufacturing, construction, installation, fuel processing, operations and maintenance, and specific information related to gender equality in the renewables sector is seldom captured in national statistics. In this context, gender budgeting is an important tool to ensure that financing of energy transition programmes and processes shifts towards outcomes that support and improve gender equality across all energy sectors.

Environmental subsystem

Some of the most vulnerable groups in energy transition are those that own, operate, or use the climate mitigation options, or those working on the manufacturing of those options at mines, processing facilities, or factories, or in the disposal of waste. For instance, many communities hosting wind farms, residing on land being proposed for biofuel crop cultivation, living in shared forests or nature reserves, or sitting adjacent to solar parks bear the brunt of negative and often concentrated social and environmental impacts. Technologically driven energy transition interventions can also impact negatively on natural ecosystem that humans depend on for their livelihood and wellbeing. Energy transition pathways and solutions require environmental, social, economic, and sustainability assessment across their whole lifecycle.

Socio-cultural subsystem

Frequently, social inequalities in low-carbon transitions are presented as four distinct power processes: enclosure (capture of land or resources), exclusion (unfair planning), encroachment (destruction of the environment), or entrenchment (worsening of inequality or vulnerability). But culture and social norms and habits can complicate and impede attempts to promote more efficient, more sustainable, and more affordable forms of energy use in homes and in buildings. Everyday routines, habits, social behaviours, aesthetic preferences and locked-in logics of consumption and mobility are important features of and may constitute significant barriers to abandoning dependence on fossil fuel-based energy system. Users don't adopt new technologies passively, but integrate them into their own practices, organisations, and routines.

Governance subsystem

Low-carbon transition pathways can entrench or cement existing power relations, including those among influential groups, advocates, political parties, or governments, where men are better integrated than women. Exclusion of women from decision-making means that alternative views and different ways of argumentation and engaging in alternative efforts to achieve the goals of the European Green Deal may be overlooked. Achieving equitable and fair energy transition means making governance more inclusive, tackling exclusion, and promoting shared prosperity and equity. It is fundamentally about altering underlying power structures and dynamics and redefining state-society relations. The extent to which governance is inclusive has to do with the extent to and ways in which people and groups that have been traditionally left out or marginalised (including women; young people; racial, ethnic, and religious groups; disabled people, transient and migrant populations, etc.) are able not only to participate but also to exert greater influence in political processes for energy transition.

Technological subsystem

Women are underrepresented and undervalued in STEM sectors, but the R&I energy research landscape is highly diverse in the range of disciplines involved and this can facilitate new career pathways and opportunities to attract more women to energy related research, innovation, and entrepreneurship. The available pool of female talent is seriously underutilised and undervalued through numerous barriers to women's participation in energy transition at all levels, which means women do not get the same opportunity as men to shape future energy systems or the 'greening' of the economy. Currently, the share of women in the renewable energy sector is marginally higher compared to the conventional energy sector, which suggests that the emerging energy areas appear to be more attractive and more welcoming to women, however, this positive image does not apply to decision-making and leadership roles. Combined with the growing interest in climate issues, particularly among young women, energy transition requires fresh, gender sensitive policy responses to accelerate actions.

Learning from the efforts of past projects

gEneSys takes into account the work of many past EU projects dedicated to advancing gender equality in research and innovation. It also draws on projects dedicated to advancing energy transition by paying attention to the social aspects of transition processes. Majority of the projects conducted so far have not included considerations of gender issues or have done so in a very limited way. gEneSys will identify and map project partnerships and extract useful lessons from the results of past projects such as: GEECCO, CALIPER, MINDtheGEPs, EFFORTI, ACT, INSPIRE, SocialRES, SONNET, PROSEU, Energy-SHIFTS, MATES RES-SKILL, W4RES, REGATRACE, ENTRANCES, GROWINPRO, EXCESS, SmartENCity, and SCALIBUR.

Building relations with current projects and programmes

The landscape of EU projects working in the areas relevant to energy transition is very crowded and it is essential to be strategic in with whom to engage to help boost impact. During the 18 months of

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

the project, dissemination efforts established connections exploring and engaging in collaborative links with a variety of projects and organisations, including:

- the DG CINEA-funded project to develop gender indicators for energy transition R&I
- LEAP-RE programme that has funded 31 projects on renewable energy under the EU-AU cooperation
- FemPower, Erasmus project
- RESET, Horizon 2020 project
- INSPIRE, Horizon Europe project
- Light on Women initiative of the European University Institute
- 23rd Gender Summit – Africa, in energy transition and green deal in Africa
- EUREC – Association of European Renewable Energy Research Centres
- EUREC Master in Renewable Energy
- Women Engage for a Common Future (WECF)
- European Energy Research Alliance (EERA)
- NET4AIR - Horizon Europe Project
- Energy Community
- EURAXXES national contact points
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Tracking gEneSys impact

The tracking of gEneSys impact on the energy transition policy, research, and implementation landscape will aim to:

- Continue to identify knowledge needs
- Continue to develop activities to deliver those needs
- Map the timing of opportunities to feed into the policy processes and R&I projects landscape
- Continue to revise and adapt efforts to identify and engage with diverse audiences.

WHAT?	HOW?	WHEN?	FOR WHO?
What new knowledge, evidence and examples of best practice are needed that gEneSys can provide?	Through which project tasks and activities can gEneSys produce the required knowledge?	What is the opportunity timeline in target projects, programmes, and initiatives that gEneSys has to keep in mind to have the intended impact?	Who are the target audiences that need new knowledge (perhaps tailored to their special needs)?

Target beneficiaries of gEneSys results and knowledge they may need

End users/beneficiaries	Promoting adoption of gender knowledge in the projects and interventions related to energy transition
Policy makers	

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

European Parliament	<p>Reliable research evidence addressing key policy issues. The Parliament can request the European Parliament Research Centre (EPRC) to assess available evidence. These briefings can be found using the EP Think Tank webpages, e.g., EP Think Tank on energy transition in Europe.</p> <p>EPRC is therefore an important communication target for gEneSys.</p>
EU agencies and programmes	
<p>DG Energy DG RTD DG REGIO DG CINEA DG INTPA DG CNECT DG EMPL DG GROW DG JUSTICE</p>	<p>The Scientific Analysis and Advice on Gender Equality (SAAGE) network provides external expertise to the European Commission in the field of gender equality policy. It includes experts in statistics, econometrics, social protection, social inclusion and labour market economists covering all 27 EU countries. The network is expected to prepare thematic reports, ad-hoc and country-specific papers covering EU countries, and organises the seminars with key gender equality experts in specific topics (not necessarily reflecting the Commission's views. At present the content available on the SAAGE website is very limited.</p> <p>In addition, the Commission may seek information through European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE). EIGE produced recently a report on gender equality in energy</p> <p>DG Justice publishes the annual report on gender equality in the EU.</p> <p>Relevant DGs, the SAAGE network members, and the experts at EIGE represent another important target for gEneSys communication efforts.</p>
R&I funding institutions	
<p>Science Europe NordForsk Vinnova DFG JRC EIC HEA Ireland NIKK Swedish Energy Agency ISC etc.,</p>	<p>The RFOs are target for gEneSys communications in the areas of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) filling in gaps in gender knowledge on energy transition by sponsoring new research studies 2) improving criteria for evaluation of gender dimensions in energy research 3) learning from gEenSys research on new methods to analyse gender issues in the energy transition

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

International organisations/initiatives	
UN Women IRENA IEA EERA EAWE OECD	integrating gender perspectives and gender knowledge into development and in particular gender sensitive implementations of SDG7
R&I performing organisations (umbrella)	
European Universities Association CESAER LERU	gEneSys can help improve understanding of: 1) gender perspective on what universities can do for energy transition (curricula, textbooks, pedagogy) 2) how to attract women to energy-related courses 3) how knowledge producers perceive energy transition 4) biases in who dominated knowledge production To maximise impact, the target for gEneSys communication in the HE area will be umbrella organisations
Civil Society, NGOs, Networks	
Women in Renewable Energy Women in Clean Tech & Sustainability Women Engage for Common Future EUI Light on Women network Women in Energy in CEE (WONY) Women of Renewable Industries and Sustainable Energy (WRISE) Nordic Energy Equality Network POWERful Women etc.,	gEneSys can cooperate with Civil Society, NGOs and Networks to: 1) understand how professional women experience work environment in energy fields 2) identify and promote role models 3) career opportunities in energy transition gEneSys will target these organisations for engagement in shared communication activities
Horizon Europe projects	
GEP and gender dimension implementing projects FemEmpower LEAP-RE projects NET4AIR Erasmus MATES RES-Skill REGATRACE GROWINPRO EXCESS	gEneSys is exploring and testing new gender-sensitive approaches for research on energy transitions and these results can be used to engage different on-going and recently completed projects in joint exchange of evidence, experience and dissemination activities. Some projects may have considered gender equality benefits as, for example, the Erasmus MATES project, which has analysed gaps in skills in Maritime Technology, and others such as RES-Skills project analysed skills needed for coal workers to find jobs in the renewable energy

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

SmartENCity SCALIBUR SocialRES SONNET W4RES ADJUST REset etc.,	industry and produced learning materials on wind technologies but have omitted considering gender equality.
Academic Journals and Social Media	
Horizon, the EU R&I Magazine Energy4Europe Africa-EU Energy Partnership Interdisciplinary Science Reviews Energy and Social Science Research Nature etc.,	Results and recommendations from gEneSys research will be communicated through targeted academic and grey publications and through social media.

Adding value in exploitation of results

gEneSys dissemination and exploitation measures are designed to add value and promote additional outcomes based on the project's results, deliverables, and outcomes from interconnections with other projects and initiatives in the energy transition ecosystem, as well as opportunities created under Erasmus+ funded projects and national NCP networks, as well as Horizon Europe NCP networks.

Key exploitable results	Target audience	Adding Value
Academic and policy publications, both peer-reviewed and as working papers, new research evidence, questions, analyses of gender dimension, results as ideas for special issue journals, fresh topics of conferences, topics for PhD, recommendations for curriculum change	Research communities, research managers, research funders, research communicators, and research editors in Europe and Africa + European Commission, African Union, and UN Agencies	Strengthening the evidence base for the EU policy strategy on gender equality in R&I, especially in Horizon Europe & the European Green Deal
The model of energy transition as a mission-oriented, gendered, innovative socio-technical ecosystem together with credible pathways to transform interrelations of power and inequality to achieve equitable, just, and fair outcomes for women and men	Policy makers, decision-makers, industry, education, Civil society/citizen organisations	Opportunities shared, implementable agendas, multistakeholder partnerships of change actors and stakeholders, greater societal engagement

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

Tested analytical approaches for international cooperation on gender sensitive implementation of SDGs and especially SDG7 (energy) with gender equality outcomes	Gender equality, SDG, and sustainability experts and practitioners	Integration of gender perspectives into all the SDG targets
Supplementary gender analysis with gender dimensions added to the 400 SSH priority research questions to	SSH and gender researchers, as well as experts and policy makers	Strengthening the evidence base and interconnections between gender and social aspect of Responsible Research and Innovation
Review of policy frameworks relevant to energy transition with opportunities/needs for gender mainstreaming	EU and national policy makers and policy impact evaluation experts	Advancing gender mainstreaming for gender equality in climate change mitigation efforts, Green New Deal, SDGs implementation, and decarbonisation goals
Demonstrations of applying tools for sex/gender analysis in research and innovation content	Research and innovation communities, research and innovation funders	Support for proposals to Horizon Europe and evaluation of impact
International Summer School at Venice University	Students	Dissemination of the principles of equity, justice and fairness in energy transition to student population
Curriculum and outreach programme to schools	Education communities, citizens	Holistic approach to energy transitions with better transfer of knowledge
Website/social presence	Everybody	Improving and widening the communication of evidence

Dialogue and knowledge sharing with stakeholders in energy

gEneSys' aim is to engage with the change actors and stakeholders in the six subsystems: political, social, economic, environmental, and technical to fully understand and influence the conceptualisations of interrelationships of power and inequality in the context of energy transitions to be more sensitive and responsive to gender inequality issues and to seeing gender equality as a lever in achieving transition.

Promoting the Gendered Innovations analytical framework

To help relevant projects and initiatives in Europe and Africa to apply gender analysis tools and intersectional perspectives to understand the barriers and obstacles to achieving equitable, inclusive, and sustainable outcomes, gEneSys will identify knowledge gaps in how gender dimension is understood in the energy transition ecosystem; how it is discussed in the context of the ambitions to ensure that results are just, fair and inclusive; and how to analyse gender dimensions of energy transition in a systematic way using the Gendered Innovations framework of 11 areas of analysis:

1. *Rethinking Research Priorities and Outcomes* which means accepting that gender differences are or may be relevant. In the context of energy transition this is particularly important when

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

assembling the evidence base to support analysis of individual subsystems and their interactions with one another.

2. *Rethinking Concepts and Theories* which means unpacking definitions (e.g., “energy transition”) and clarifying understanding of the wording used when energy transition is debated, e.g., “just transition”, “energy poverty” etc. This helps understand the influence of formal and informal social institutions, social norms, and gender stereotypes of human behaviour.
3. *Formulating Research Questions* which is about scoping the analytical approach to identify gender-related power hierarchies in energy systems (traditional and emerging). The relevant gender question can be for instance how to ensure societal acceptance of radical innovations and understand impacts of environmental degradation of energy infrastructures on women’s livelihoods and health.
4. *Analysing Sex* means paying attention to essential, unchangeable biological differences and how they influence response to energy poverty, hunger, disease, or changes in environmental conditions, for instance due to polluting household cooking equipment.
5. *Analysing Gender* means understanding socio-cultural norms and stereotypes used in society to label an individual as male or female and recognising how socio-cultural differences and inequalities between women and men are maintained by social institutions.
6. *Analysing how Sex and Gender Interact* means considering both biological and socio-cultural perspectives on the role and behaviours of women and men. For instance, tracking impact of greenhouse gas emissions may involve understanding the gendered nature of energy consumption as it relates to work, or within the household, and how it relates to health and wellbeing.
7. *Intersectional Approaches* means paying attention to other human characteristics such as age, social status, education, ethnicity, race, geography, that play a role in defining vulnerability through lack of access to energy supply.
8. *Engineering Innovation Processes* means creating socio-technical systems to ensure that energy transition pathways and low-carbon technologies do not propagate gender inequalities embedded in existing technologies. As an example, solar panels are particularly difficult to dismantle, which makes attempts to recycle the components very difficult, contributing to accumulation of electronic waste, but also restricting opportunities for creating employment for women in electronic waste processing sector.
9. *Co-creation and Participatory Research* means involving multiple actors and stakeholders in analysis of problems and generation of proposals for solutions. In the context of energy transitions this may mean including the voices of rural, poor, indigenous, or other marginalized communities.
10. *Rethinking Standards and Reference Models* means removing gender bias in energy transition through, for example, enhancing transparency and traceability in procurement of resources, products, and services to ensure availability and price of energy.
11. *Rethinking Language and Visual Representations* means demonstrating the gendered nature of energy transition in a way that can be easily comprehended by non-gender experts and lay persons. This could be by using images, graphics, stories when communicating rationales for gendered energy transitions etc.

Dialogue focused on the policy subsystem

The key elements in the policy subsystem for gEneSys are the 2020-2025 Gender Equality Strategy (GES) and the third Gender Action Plan (GAP III), the 2021-2027 Multi-annual Financial Framework (MFF), Horizon Europe, and the 2021-2027 Cohesion Plan and Fund. The key objectives of GES are:

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

ending gender-based violence; challenging gender stereotypes; closing gender gaps in the labour market; achieving equal participation across different sectors of the economy; addressing the gender pay and pension gaps; closing the gender care gap; and achieving gender balance in decision-making and in politics.

Participating in the dialogue focused on the technology subsystem

The focus of dissemination activities in the technological subsystem are the European Sustainable Energy Week, the European Strategic Energy Technology Plan, its nine European Technology Innovations Platforms, and the members of the European Energy Research Alliance (250 organisations in 30 countries) who are at the forefront of technological innovation. In addition, gEneSys aims to enrich understanding how gender fits into the recommendations made in the 2017 EUA report on Energy Transition and the Future of Energy Research, Innovation and Education: An Action Agenda for European Universities.

The EUA report stresses that achieving a low carbon economy involves tackling uncertainty and ambiguity about future energy supply, the energy mix, energy use and efficiency and working out how to address behavioural change and adaptation, and that universities are key stakeholders in energy transition. These dissemination actions are needed because of the persistent underrepresentation of women in SET fields reported by She Figures.

gEneSys aims to engage with stakeholders advancing technological solutions for energy transition, as well as with the EU (virtual) multidisciplinary Energy Transition Expertise Centre (EnTEC), created to monitor and analyse trends in technologies and innovations that are relevant for the energy transition, in the energy sector but also in other relevant sectors, including the organisation that have participated in the EUA consultation.

Participating in the dialogue focused on society

In relation to the societal subsystem, the gEneSys dissemination activities aim to raise awareness of the missed gender dimensions in the evidence and outcomes of several recent EU energy related projects such as the EU Energy-Shifts project, which identified 400 social science and humanities priority research questions in four energy areas (100 questions each): renewables, smart consumption, energy efficiency and transport and mobility. One of the gEneSys consortium partners, Jagiellonian University, has been involved in the Energy-Shifts project and will take this task on. Other projects where gender dimension needs analysis include: ECHOES and its theoretical concepts of 'energy collectives' and 'energy memories'; ENABLE.EU which conducted household surveys to understand the factors that drive energy choices in daily life; ENERGISE, which developed methods to transform energy use in households; SMARTTEES which developed the concept of social energy innovation; CHEETAH which assessed how policy interventions break down barriers to energy efficient choices; PENNY, which studied psychological, social, economic and financial factors in the residential sectors, and ASSET that addressed the challenge of a rapidly evolving energy sector that requires creating new job opportunities, re-skilling the workforce, and the development of new interdisciplinary skills and expertise.

Participating in the dialogue focused on environment

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

The gEneSys dissemination activities in the context of environmental subsystem target the EU strategy for achieving net-zero GHG emissions by 2050 while sustaining economic growth as set out in the European Green Deal (COM(2019)640 final) and has been followed by legislative texts, including the 2021 Climate Law. There was no Impact Assessment conducted for the 2021 Climate Law. European Union (EU) energy policies aim to deliver on the EU's Paris Agreement commitments through a Clean Energy Transition which encourages greater efficiency, and the use of low carbon energy sources to replace fossil fuels.

The EU clean and fair energy transition aims to create a more secure, competitive, and sustainable energy system that supports economic growth and improves the quality of life of its citizens. EU Clean energy for all Europeans legislative acts aim to place the citizen at the centre of the energy transition.

Participating in the dialogue focused on governance

The new energy policy is Europe's response to the impacts of COVID pandemic and the war in Ukraine is the REPowerEU policy priority for more affordable, secure, and sustainable energy. The European Green Capital is relevant to understand transitions in labour markets. Strongly relevant to the advancement of gender equality in energy sectors is the EU Directive on Work-life Balance, Recast Directive (2006/54/EC on gender equality and non-discrimination, developments in ERA and EHEA, the European Social Charter of the Council of Europe, Ljubljana Declaration, and the European Parliament's call for Cooperation between EU and Africa on SDGs.

gEneSys dissemination at the governance subsystem level aims to target, in particular, the DGs that are responsible for the energy transition-related programmes funded under the MFF 2021-2027 strategy.

Participation in the dialogue focused on Africa and SDGs

Ensuring a joint EU-AU Green transition means working together towards a low-carbon, resource efficient and climate-resilient future in line with the Paris Agreement. The EU addresses these priorities through its European Green Deal, complemented by the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, the EU Farm to Fork Strategy and others. The AU guiding continental flagship is Africa's Agenda 2063, with the CAADP and Malabo Declaration, the AU SPS Policy Framework, the AU Wildlife Strategy, the AU Sustainable Forest Management Framework, the AU Blue Economy Strategy and others contributing to it.

gEneSys dissemination activities in this part of the project aim to use the 2023 Gender Summit – Africa on Africa's energy transition pathways and green deal to engage with actors outside the Consortium. Following from this event, gEneSys has connected with the EU-AU collaborative program LEAP-RE, which funds 31 projects on developing renewable energy solutions to take joint actions on advancing gender dimension and gender equality benefits into these projects.

On-line access to key resources

gEneSys aims to make its website as the target for up-to-date, impactful information, advice, and co-operation activities on advancing understanding of gender issues in energy transition. For this,

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

gEneSys will post its own resources: the outputs and deliverables from the different work packages and links to the key resources that underpin the projects work. It will also feature important resources produced by the organisations with whom the project will co-operate, such as topical research review-based blogs, learning materials, guidelines etc.

Conferences and events

gEneSys will prioritise opportunities for speaker-level participation in conferences and events but also will endeavour to take part in events where virtual participation is enabled. gEneSys has a plan to organise two international conference events) and six participatory workshops/webinars..

Since the project has started, the project was represented in the following events:

- Public event introducing gEneSys organised as part of the kick-off meeting (March 2023)
- As a dedicated speaker panel made up of Consortium Partners, in a parallel on-line session in the 23rd Gender Summit – Africa, which had as the theme Africa’s energy transition pathways and green deal through the gender lens (May 2023)
- Interactive Exhibition Booth at GS23 on-line conference platform
- As speakers and moderators in the in-person GS23 programme that took place in Ghana
- The European Sustainable Energy Conference, as participant (May 2023) (a dedicated session was proposed but was not approved by the organisers)
- The Light on Women awards event, as participant (June 2023)
- The International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators, as member of the in-person special session speaker panel (September 2023)
- Participatory workshop organised and hosted at Energy, Environment and Societies in Crises, September 2023
- Consultation workshop on gender indicators in energy transition R&I, as invited participant (October 2023)
- Italian Regional Conference on Complex Systems (October 2023), speaker on Monitoring the Women's empowerment in the Italian Information System Community
- XX Conference of the Italian Chapter of AIS - BUSINESS AND PEOPLE ECOSYSTEMS IN THE DIGITAL SOCIETY (October 2023), as speaker on Women's Resilience in the Time of Covid-19
- Joint open webinar with DG CINEA funded project on gender balance in energy transition R&I (October 2023)
- World Forum for Women in Science, as speaker (April 2024)
- 24th Gender Summit – Europe, invited to host a parallel session(May 2024)
- Joint open webinar with LEAP-RE (June 2024)
- EUBCE conference (June 2024) as speaker on "Gendering energy and bioeconomy pathways"
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Later in the project, gEneSys will organise a one-week summer school hosted by the Venice International University (VIU) in Venice that will involve 20 students from different countries. Students will be selected through an open call that will be disseminated through the consortium partners’ networks, as well as, through the Venice International University network that includes universities and research institutions from North America, Europe, Africa, Middle East, and Asia.

Communication

gEneSys aims to achieve impact by pro-actively promoting gender equality as a lever (rather than a barrier) in achieving equitable, just, and fair processes and outcomes in energy transition, the European Green Deal, climate change mitigation efforts, and SDGs implementation. An example

target are members of the European Energy Research Alliance with more than 175 research organisations from 27 countries, involved in 17 joint programmes. Communication efforts will aim to promote multistakeholder, multidisciplinary understanding of the consequences of gender inequality and their intersectional aspects in energy transition and in the sustainability goals, and of the need for inclusive and shared responsibility of power and decision making to achieve equitable, fair and just processes and outcomes.

Website

The website aims to provide information about the project itself and its goals but also to act as a source of gender-related information for organisations and projects active in energy transition processes:

- To help change actors and stakeholders in the six subsystems: political, social, economic, environmental, and technical to improve their understanding of the interrelationships of power and inequality in the context of energy transitions and be more sensitive and responsive to gender inequality issues and to seeing gender equality as a lever in achieving transition.
- To promote the project's vision of energy transition as a mission-oriented, gendered, socio-technical innovation ecosystem and open multiple opportunities for fresh discourses on how different institutions/sectors and professions can shape the conceptual landscape of energy transition to create robust and socially responsible technological innovations that are equitable, fair, and just.
- To point out example of gender blind or biased thinking and the consequences of gender inequality and their intersectional aspects in energy transition and in the sustainability goals,
- To shape evidence and arguments to ensure well focused and implementable recommendations for action at the level of policy, knowledge, technology, societal

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

involvement, and socio-economic development that respond to the agendas of the different change actors and stakeholders in energy transition.

- To improve understanding of power-gender relations, processes, and outcomes in energy transition and better agendas for gender equality in the European Green Deal, climate change mitigation efforts and Sustainable Development Goals.

Communication channels and materials

gEneSys has established a visual identity and a presence on LinkedIn and Twitter. Collaborative links have been established with the European Universities Institute and the Horizon 2020 programme LEAP-RE, as well as the CINEA-funded project developing gender indicators for energy transition R&I.

Interactive exhibition booth at the 23rd Gender Summit - Africa

The specific channels and measures that will be targeted are summarised below.

Channels	Materials and outputs
Academic and policy publications	<p>Expected 2 x research papers submitted/year, 3 x Working Papers, and 6 x policy briefs</p> <p>Achieved/in progress</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A report from the 23rd Gender Summit – Africa • Paper submitted to Energy and Social Science Research • Collection of papers are under preparations for the special issue of Interdisciplinary Science Reviews journal
Presentations	<p>Expected: 6 x conference presentations in external events</p> <p>Achieved/in progress</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May 2023: special session at the 23rd Gender Summit-Africa • September 2023: joint session at the International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators • May 2024: Exhibition Booth at the 24th Gender Summit- Europe

D.6.2 REVIEW AND UPDATE OF COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND IMPACT STRATEGY

Synergistic interlinkages with change actors, stakeholders, and projects	<p>Expected: 6 x joint activities (webinars, high level dialogues, joint workshops/co-creation events)</p> <p>Achieved/in progress</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultations with the European Universities Institute on promoting women in energy transition as part of their Light on Women initiative • Webinars with LEAP-RE on gender equality issues in renewable energy • Webinar with DG CINEA funded project on gender balance in energy transition R&I • Webinar with GISTeR on gender innovation indicators
Policy workshops	<p>Expected: 3 x workshops 30-40 attendees (in person and on-line)</p> <p>Achieved/in progress</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As part of INSPIRE project policy workshop – to help contextualise policy recommendations on gender equality to include energy and green deal (October 2023) • As part of Empirica project on gender indicators in energy Transition R&I – to help validate perspectives on gender equality in energy transition scenarios (October 2023) • As part of forthcoming 1st Conference in October 2024
Social media	<p>Expected: 1000 followers</p>
Website	<p>Expected: 10,000 hits</p>
Conference	<p>Expected: 300 attendees</p>
Project information	Leaflets, posters, summaries